

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON GARA VISHA AND DOOSHI VISHA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHRONIC TOXICITY

Ankur Mishra*¹, Niharika²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Agadtantra Evam Vidhi Vaidyak.

²U.G. Scholar Mai Bhago Ayurvedic Medical College for Women & Hospital.

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*Corresponding Author

Ankur Mishra

Assistant Professor, Department of
Agadtantra Evam Vidhi Vaidyak.

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, due to better access to education, media, and healthcare information, people are more aware of common and easily encountered types of poisons. But what about the hidden and concocted poisons? People knowingly or unknowingly are exposed to these poisons, which has led to an increased rate of serious diseases such as cancer, heart failure, and kidney disorders.^[1] In Ayurveda, these poisons are explained as *Gara Visha* and *Dooshi Visha*. Acharya Charaka describes *Gara Visha* as *Sanyogaja Visha*, which is different from *Sthavara* (plant origin) and *Jangama* (animal origin) poisons, *Gara Visha* refers to a combination form of poison, formed when two or more individually non-poisonous substances, when combined together and become toxic.^[2] Acharya Sushruta describes *Dooshi Visha* as a type of poison that remains in the body for a

long time and gradually produces ill effects. Acharya Bhavaprakasha classifies both *Gara Visha* and *Dooshi Visha* under *Kritrima Visha* (artificial poisons).

Incompatible drugs in a formulation and those *Visha Yogas* with less potency can also be incorporated under this category. Some examples of *Gara Visha* in our day-to-day life include alcoholic beverages, carbonated drinks, and interestingly, certain cosmetic products also fall into this group.^[3] On the other hand, *Dooshi Visha* includes cases of occupational poisoning due to heavy metals such as lead, mercury, and copper, as well as chronic exposure to pesticides and herbicidal sprays commonly used by farmers.

Both *Gara Visha* and *Dooshi Visha* do not cause the instantaneous death of a person, as they require time to get metabolized within the body. Thus, they are considered as slow-acting and accumulated poisons, producing harmful effects gradually rather than immediately.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1. To study the general concepts of *Gara Visha* and *Dooshi Visha*.
2. To study about the clinical manifestations of *Gara Visha* and *Dooshi Visha*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article is based on different Ayurvedic texts, contemporary literature, e-journals, internet, and other available sources.

CLINICAL MANIFESTATION

Literature Review

According to *Acharya Vagbhatta* and *Madhavakara*

Clinical Manifestations of *Gara Visha*

Some women, for the purpose of attaining good fortune (or for enchanting/controlling others – *Vashikaran*), mix sweat, menstrual blood, various bodily excretions, and even *gara* or combined poisons administered by enemies into food and give it to a person.^[4]

As a result, that person develops

- Pale (yellowish) complexion (*Pāṇḍu-varṇa*),
- Emaciation/thinness,
- Weak digestive fire (*Manda-agni*),

And thus the formation of *Gara-visha* (slow/concocted poison) in the body.

From this, the following symptoms and diseases may also appear:

- Pain in vital organs (*Marmavyathā*),
- Abdominal distension (*Ādhmāna*),
- Swelling in the hands,
- Abdominal disorders (*Udararoga*),
- *Grahaṇī* disease (chronic digestive disorder),
- Tuberculosis-like illness (*Yakṣmā*),
- Abdominal tumors or lumps (*Gulma*),
- Wasting disease (*Kṣaya*),

- Fever (*Jvara*),
- And many other similar ailments.

Acharya Vagbhatta has also mentioned

- Dream symptoms:
Such a person, in dreams, sees jackals, cats, mongooses, wild animals, monkeys, dry forests, and reservoirs of water.^[5]
- A dark-complexioned person sees himself as fair, while a fair person sees himself as dark.
- He perceives his own face as devoid of ears, nose, and eyes, and feels as if his senses are destroyed.

According to *Acharya Sushruta*

Clinical Manifestations of Dooshi Visha

- If *Dooshi Visha* is located in the stomach (*āmāśaya*), then due to obstruction of *Vāta* by *Kapha*, *Kapha-Vāta* disorders arise.^[6]
- If this poison remains in the large intestine (*pakvāsaya*), the patient suffers from *Vāta-Pitta* disorders, and because of the falling of hair from the head and body, the patient appears like a bird with clipped wings.
- When *Dooshi Visha* is situated in the body tissues such as *Rasa* and *Rakta*, it produces symptoms in the *dhātus*, like loss of appetite, dislike for food, etc.,
- Its aggravation occurs quickly in cold winds and cloudy days.

In the prodromal stage (*pūruvarūpa-avasthā*), *Dooshi Visha* produces

- sleepiness,
- heaviness,
- excessive yawning,
- laxity,
- horripilation,
- and weakness of the body.

Later, in the manifested stage (*rūpāvasthā*),^[7]

- after indigestion, it creates a condition resembling intoxication,
- anorexia,
- appearance of circular patches on the skin,

- muscular wasting,
- swelling of hands and feet,
- fainting,
- vomiting,
- diarrhea,
- painful micturition,
- intermittent fever,
- and abdominal enlargement.

MODERN REVIEW

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF *GARA VISHA* AND *DOOSHI VISHA*

- Contact Dermatitis^[8]
- Eczema
- Psoriasis like lesions
- Syncope
- Chronic liver disease
- Malaise
- Liver disorders
- Abdominal tumors
- CNS depression
- Hypersomnia
- Cardiac arrhythmia

CONCLUSION

Both *Gara Visha* and *Dooshi Visha* are forms of slow-acting, accumulated poisons described in Ayurveda that do not cause immediate death but gradually deteriorate health, leading to chronic, multi-system disorders.

Gara Visha (concocted/combined poison) arises mainly from artificial mixtures of incompatible, impure, or intentional poisonous substances often administered secretly. Its manifestations include pallor, emaciation, weak digestion, abdominal disorders, wasting diseases, and even abnormal dream experiences. It creates a state of persistent ill-health, resembling modern descriptions of chronic toxicity and psychosomatic disturbances.

Dooshi Visha (latent/accumulated poison) results when small doses of natural poisons, toxins, or improperly digested substances remain in the body for long periods. It localizes in the stomach, intestines, and *dhātus*, producing digestive, hematological, and systemic disorders. Its symptoms worsen under cloudy, cold conditions and progress from prodromal signs like heaviness and yawning to major conditions such as anorexia, skin changes, edema, fainting, and wasting.

DISCUSSION

The *Ayurvedic* classics present *Gara Visha* and *Dooshi Visha* as two important categories of slow-acting poisons that differ in their origin but overlap in their clinical picture.

Pathogenesis

Gara Visha is generally externally administered, often as an artificial mixture of incompatible substances or deliberate poison given with food or drink.

Dooshi Visha, in contrast, arises within the body when small, sub-lethal quantities of natural poisons or undigested toxic materials accumulate over time and are not completely eliminated.

Clinical features

Gara Visha produces classical signs like pallor, wasting, abdominal disorders, weak digestion, and unusual dream states. These point towards chronic metabolic impairment and neuro-psychological disturbances.

Dooshi Visha manifests first with subtle prodromal symptoms like heaviness, yawning, and lassitude, later progressing to systemic disorders such as anorexia, edema, wasting, and intermittent fevers. These symptoms suggest long-standing subclinical poisoning with systemic deterioration.

Aggravating factors

Dooshi Visha is specifically aggravated by cold winds and cloudy days, showing its strong dependence on environmental triggers, whereas *Gara Visha* is more directly linked with dietary intake and intentional administration.

Modern co-relation

Both concepts can be correlated to conditions of chronic toxicity, metabolic poisoning, autoimmune-like manifestations, and cumulative effects of toxins such as heavy metals, pesticides, drugs, or incompatible food combinations. *Gara Visha* parallels artificial toxic exposures, while *Dooshi Visha* resembles chronic accumulation of sub-threshold toxins.

Thus, *Ayurveda* gives a unique insight into chronic poisoning, much broader than acute toxicology, by emphasizing slow, hidden, and cumulative effects that mimic several chronic diseases of modern medicine.

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